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Sanitation in practice. An experience of traditional pit latrine use in Tanzania.

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Abstract

The paper is about the use of traditional pit latrines in Tanzania. The study analyses data from the baseline and end line household surveys conducted between 2011 and 2014 in Tanzania. While the findings show that there is no significant change in the use of traditional pit latrines in the rural areas, on the one hand, they show that there is an increase of use of traditional pit latrines in the urban areas and in Tanzania in general. While the no change situation in rural areas is attributed to the no need attitude where availability of bushes, forest, and farm lands provide option for practicing open defecation, the increased use in urban areas and in Tanzania in general is attributed to efforts of improving hygiene by the state and the assignment to the head of household by the National Sanitation and Hygiene Policy of 2009. The study concludes that the increase of traditional pit latrines is an indication of the reduction of open defecation, implying that there is the positive change in the improved toilet facility use. The study recommends for more efforts in the rural areas to make a follow up to the head of household to be more accountable for toilet construction and use and promotion of "micro" land use planning at the household level and promotion of ventilated pit latrine toilet facilities whereby proper procedures to identify and allocate space for a toilet facility on the household plot is necessary.

Keywords: sanitation, defecation, toileting practices, pit latrines

1.0 Introductory background

1.1 Understanding sanitation

The word sanitation is a derivative of a Latin word *sanus*, meaning sound, healthy, sensible. This etymological meaning has gone on characterizing the understanding of sanitation in the realm of water and sewage disposal, and thus conceptualizing sanitation as processes for a provision of clean water and adequate disposal of sewage (Black & Fawcett, 2008; URT, 2009; Chand & White, 2015).

This concept of sanitation, however, has more related concepts such as basic sanitation, on-site sanitation, food sanitation, environmental sanitation, and ecological sanitation (UNICEF/WHO, 2008; URT, 2009; George, 2010; David, 2014). Basic sanitation is described as having access to minimum standards of facilities acceptable for the safe disposal of human excreta, as well as the ability to maintain hygienic conditions, through practices such as garbage collection, hazardous waste management, and wastewater treatment and disposal (Black & Fawcett, 2008). The on-site sanitation refers to the practices of collection and treatment of waste at the area where they are generated (Kaseva, & Mbuligwe, 2007; URT, 2009; Hozefa, 2011). Food sanitation is about practices that ensure food safety. These include the way it is prepared and stored before consumption (WHO, 1992; UNICEF/WHO, 2008; URT, 2009; Hozefa, 2011). Environmental sanitation relates to controlling of environmental practices that are linked to disease transmissions, such as poor solid waste management, water and wastewater treatment, industrial treatment and noise pollution control (URT, 2009; Hozefa, 2011; Majitaka, n.d; Government of India, 2015). An ecological sanitation practice applies ecosystem view to sanitation, whereby it perceives wastes as resources within the system (Langergraber & Mullegger, 2005; Shayo, 2007; Kasseva & Mbuligwe, 2007; Devine & Kullmann, 2011).

The idea of health is central to sanitation. What, however, has been dominant in the sanitation discourse is this understanding of sanitation from the perspective of sanitation as having to do with hygienic conditions. Hygiene is a derivative of Greek: *hygies* in Greek means healthy or living well. In Greek mythology, this makes reference to the goddess Hygeia, who is the goddess of good health (Wright, 1967; Kasper, 2013). Hygeia was the Goddess of good health. She was a daughter and attendant of the medicine-god who

was called Asklepios, and a companion of the Goddess Aphrodite. This Goddess has two sisters, Panakeia (All-cure) and Iaso (Remedy). Hygeia had enemies, Nosoi (Spirits of disease).

It was not until in 1939 when the notion sanitation was used for the first time to refer to promotion of hygiene through prevention of human contact with hazards of human faeces (UNICEF, 1986; Benidickson, 2007), a notion that was also adopted by the World Health Organisation (WHO) (UNICEF, 1986). For example, the WHO defined sanitation as generally referring “to the provision of facilities and services for the safe disposal of human urine and faeces” (UNICEF/WHO, 2008:1). It is in this line that sanitation has been taken as an important factor in improving health and dignity of the people (URT, 2009; George, 2010; WHO/UNICEF, 2015a).

Sanitation in public health has come to be related to the practices of preventing transmission of diseases from human excreta, which affects human beings (Benidickson, 2007; WHO/UNICEF, 2015b). Estimates made by the WHO in 2015 show that about 5 million people worldwide die each year because of poor sanitation practices (WHO/UNICEF, 2015b). For instance, in 2015, the World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) reported that only 68% of the world population had access to improved sanitation facilities (WHO/UNICEF, 2015b). The situation caused human health risk including death (WHO/UNICEF, 2015c). Globally, unimproved sanitation costs estimated by the World Bank in 2015 are around \$260 billion yearly (UNICEF, 2015; WSSCC, 2016; Rognerud & Fonseca, 2016). In the same period, the WHO estimated that 1 US Dollar spent in improved sanitation saved 5.50 US dollars in health costs, reduced premature deaths and increased productivity (WSSCC, 2016; Rognerud, & Fonseca, 2016). Therefore, sanitation is an important element of public health management and achieving better sanitations services should be the goal for any human society.

1.2 Tanzania and sanitation policy environment

Until 2009 Tanzania had no independent policy to guide sanitation and hygiene provision in the country in its full context (Hozefa, 2011; Tremolet & Binder, 2013). The Tanzania National Sanitation and Hygiene Policy of 2009 have the following focus:

This policy focuses on the sanitation and hygiene which breaks the fecal – oral transmission chain, which means preventing fecal matter from reaching the mouth. However,

due to the interconnectedness of the various elements of environmental sanitation and their impacts on health, the broader elements of environmental sanitation and hygiene, have also been touched upon in various sections (URT, 2009: 4).

While the broad objective of the policy is “*To improve sanitation and hygiene practices in the community with the focus on improved health and quality of life*” (URT, 2009: 11), the specific objectives are:

To sensitize the community on behavioural changes towards improved hygiene and sanitation practices.

To mobilize communities, including school communities to form water, sanitation, and hygiene user groups, charged with the duties of ensuring sustained improved water supply, hygiene and sanitation.☒

To enhance collaboration for transformed hygiene practices, sanitation and water supply in crucial areas including households, schools, institutions and in public and in private places.

To reduce morbidity and mortality due to poor hygiene and sanitation by improving water supply, sanitation and hygiene in an integrated manner (URT, 2009: 11-12).

What is said within the WHO circles, particularly the hygiene issue, is clearly echoed in the Tanzanian policy dealing with sanitation and hygiene: the policy focuses on the sanitation and hygiene; to improve sanitation and hygiene; sensitize the community on behavioral changes towards improved hygiene and sanitation practices; etc (Chieh-sheng, 2002).

Tanzania is not behind the discussions about sanitation for the Post-2015. In March 2013, Tanzania had a consultative meeting on water, with an idea to support the Post 2015 Development Agenda. Such standards that are set are a source of sanitation problematization (Kamugisha, 2013). In this meeting, with regard to sanitation, some key priorities were set in order to ensure access to safe and sustainable drinking water, sanitation and hygiene services, namely: availability of financial resources, appropriate environment friendly technologies and adequate consideration of cultural and spiritual concerns, more research for development to improve delivery on WASH, education and awareness creation at all levels by all stakeholders, managing the transition from MDGs to SDGs, adequate

coordination and communication among key institutions dealing with WASH, better linkages between WASH and Water Resource Management (WRM), harmonization of conflicting legal frameworks, and strengthening of public-Private Partnerships in dealing with sanitation issues (Kamugisha, 2013: 4). This consultation meeting for Tanzanians came two years later, after the consultations of the WHO/UNICEF in 2011. More than stipulating targets, it prioritizes means that could be used to achieve the targets (idem).

1.3 Sanitation and defecation

The sanitation discourse has to do with the problematization of sanitation based on hygiene. People's health, among other things, is related to the level and quality of sanitation services provided to the community (Pathak, 2011). Provision of poor sanitation services may result to high incidences of transmitted diseases. In his foreword for the first Tanzania National Sanitation and Hygiene Policy of 2009, the Minister for Health and Social Welfare noted that:

Environmental health and sanitation have been given a low profile in development programmes in the country. ... overall, the current status of hygiene and sanitation in Tanzania is characterised as one suffering from chronic neglect (URT, 2009: 2).

The neglect could be associated with the historical little attention given to human defecation practices worldwide as noted by Pathak (1995:1):

Unlike body functions like dance, drama, and songs, defecation is considered very lowly. As a result, very few scholars documented precisely the toilet habits of our predecessors. The Nobel Prize winner for Medicine (1913) Charles Richet attributes this silence to the disgust that arises from noxiousness and lack of usefulness of human waste. Others point out that as sex organs are the same or nearer to the organs of defecation, those who dared to write on toilet habits were dubbed either as erotic or as vulgar and, thus, despised in academic and social circles. It was true for example of Urdu poets in India, English poets in Britain and French poets in France (Pathak, 1995:1).

In the medical sciences, defecation is taken as the end act in the digestion process whereby the human body removes unwanted materials from the digestive tract through the anus (Deeb, 2004). The action of removing unwanted materials from the body is as important as breathing to a human being (Deeb, 2004; George, 2010). The

removed materials are commonly known as human excreta, stool or faeces (Heaton, et al., 1992; Deeb, 2004; George, 2010). The process and frequency of removing faeces from the human body are mostly involuntary though in some few cases some people have managed to make it regular (Heaton, et al., 1992; Deeb, 2004). Defecation though an important human function is the least studied, discussed and little documented by social scientists (Heaton, et al., 1992; Pathak, 1995; Van der Geest, 2007; George, 2010; Kasper, 2013).

According to Smith (2002) and Rigg, et al., (2009), there are two major concerns with excreta and urine. The first concern is about excreta and urine as a source of contamination; excreta and urine can have germs and attract more germs; insects, such as flies, easily spread these germs; it is for this matter that excreta and urine are the source of epidemics, such as cholera. Once excreta and urine are seen as the source of contamination, then, the resulting handling practices become means to efficiently remove excreta and urine to avoid public health risk. The second concern is about excreta and urine as the resource. Some people consider excreta and urine as nutrients for animals, fish and birds (Berling, et al., 2013). Others consider excreta as the nutrient for the soil. For example, farmers have the possibility to relieve themselves on their way to the farm or on their farm; for example, 64% of farmers in Ghana and Mali were using human waste as fertilizer on their farm (Van der Geest & Obirih-Opareh, 2008). Among some people, excreta have got magical powers (Van der Geest, 2007; Akpabio, 2012); excreta are also the source of minerals, such as gold, calcium, sodium, and phosphorus (Nashimuta, et al, 2006). Once excreta and urine are seen as the resource, then the handling practices become means to efficiently harness the resourcefulness; this could be in terms of recycling and/or mineral extraction (Smith, 2002; Nashimuta, et al, 2006; Rigg, et al., 2009).

So, defecation that results into excreta and urine is, basically, linked to two main concerns of being noxious and at the same time being useful. When noxious, the handling practices tend to struggle to efficiently minimize contact with humans and other agents that could enhance the spread of infections from them; when useful, the handling practices tend to struggle to efficiently harness the resources in them. These handling practices are what are referred to as toileting practices in this study.

1.4 Sanitation and toileting practices

The globe has become characterized by the concern for having toilets, particularly in developing countries where the major concern is to improve toilet facilities coverage and reduce open defecation practices (Kar & Chambers, 2008; Kasper, 2013; Rognerud, & Fonseca, 2016; Chambers & Myers, 2016). This is because, according to Mara and Alabaster (2008), many people in developing countries are still involved in open defecation and have no access to improved sanitation. These people either practice open defecation or other forms of unimproved sanitation such as open pit latrines that are associated with health hazard and sometimes cause death (Mara & Alabaster, 2008; WHO/UNICEF, 2012; WHO/UNICEF, 2015a).

It is due to this problematization with the sanitation discourse that there are efforts made by international, regional and countries' organizations to improve access to sanitation. For example, WHO/UNICEF made estimate that in 2000, Asia spent 15% while Latin America spent 38% of the money allocated for water and sanitation to fund sanitation programmes. In the same period, Africa spent 12% of the money allocated for water and sanitation to fund sanitation (Devine & Kullmann, 2011). Also, different approaches for sanitation progress have been used whereby for rural areas, latrine construction turns out to be the custom for sanitation improvement. Community-Led Total Sanitation (CLTS) has been established using Participatory Development (PD) approaches after recognition that provision of physical infrastructure alone cannot necessarily lead to improved sanitation practices (Kar, & Chambers, 2008; Kasper, 2013). According to Rognerud, & Fonseca, (2016), African leaders agreed to spend 0.5% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of their respective countries.

Toileting practices by humans have displayed considerable variation among people (Pathak, 1995; Chambers & Myers, 2016). Toileting practices have been a human beings' concern as soon as they started to live as a group (Smith, 2002; Pathak, 1995; Welshman, 2005). The practices range from "open" to "closed" defecation. Open defecation refers to the discharge of faeces from the body in fields and/or in water or close to water sources (Kar & Chambers, 2008; Bhattacharya, et al., 2011:2). Mara and Alabaster (2008) and WHO/UNICEF (2012) reveal that in developing countries, many people are still involved in open defecation. It is estimated that about 946 million (13%) of the population worldwide practice open

defecation (WHO/UNICEF, 2015b). It was similarly reported that about 2.4 billion people, equivalent to 32% had no improved sanitation (ibid). In addition to that, it is also reported that about 946 million people, or around 13% of the world population practice open air defecation, that is, defecation in the fields, forests, bushes, water bodies and other open spaces (WHO/UNICEF, 2015a). In Latin America and the Caribbean, approximately 120 million people (45%) practice open defecation (WHO/UNICEF, 2010). In India, for example, about half the population (626 million people) mostly those in rural areas practice open defecation followed by Indonesia (54 million people), and Pakistan (41 million people) (UNICEF, 2014). According to Babalobi (2015), 233 million people still practice open defecation in Africa. The majority of the people are found in Nigeria with 39 million, followed by 34 million for Ethiopia, 17 million for Sudan, 13 for Niger, 10 for Mozambique, 9 each for Burkina Faso and Madagascar, 8 each for South Sudan and Chad, and 6 for Tanzania. The remaining parts of Africa together have 80 million people (UNICEF, 2014).

Open defecation in Western European history was demanded as a right in the eighteenth century. According to Pathak (1995), people in Europe demanded the right to practice open defecation to maintain traditional toileting practices, as can be evidenced in France:

A number of enactments, however, could not prevent people to defecate in the open. A delegation led by master weaver protested in front of the French Municipal Building and said "our fathers have defecated at the place where you prevent us from doing. We have defecated here and now our children will defecate there (Pathak, 1995:4). ☒

Open defecation in this context is demanded to be practiced as something of the past. It is a demand to maintain a tradition, which is perceived as lost. Europe, however, has gone way far from open defecation to closed defecation practices, which refer to the discharge of faeces from the body in human-made facilities intended to handle excreta and urine.

According to the "Guidelines for Human Settlement Planning and Design" by the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR, 2000), closed defecation practices can be grouped into four categories. Group one is for chemical toilets for temporary use only. Group two is for ventilated improved pit toilets, ventilated improved double-pit toilets, ventilated vault toilets, and urine diversion toilets.

Group three is for flushing toilets with conservancy tank and shallow sewers. Group four is for aqua-privy toilets. This categorization is based on "conveyance", that is, whether the toilets need conveyance or not. For the category of toilets that require the conveyance of defecated material to a treatment place (off-site treatment, we have group 1 and 3 toilets). For the category of toilets that do not need conveyance, that is, toilets whose treatment or partial treatment is on site, we have group 2 and 4 toilets (Idem). Additionally, different from this categorization, there are the so-called "flying toilets"; some people use plastic bags as private toilets; they defecate in them and throw away the bag and the content. Toilet bags seem to be useful and simple to handle because they are easy to carry and dispose of. As Van der Geest and Obirih-Opareh (2008:216) noted: "It seems an attractive compromise: one can defecate at home and yet one is not stuck with the unpleasant presence of a permanent toilet in the home". This is because other people consider toilet as a nuisance and something to be away from home (Van der Geest, 2007: Chambers & Myers, 2016). It is the concern about cleanliness that accounts for the reluctance of people to build a toilet in their house; such people consider a toilet, by definition, as a dirty place; this implies that it should be kept outside the house, even though defecation can be done in the house.

This study deals with the traditional pit latrines. These are types of toilet facilities that collect human fecal material in a hole in the ground; they do not use water for conveyance; it is for this matter that they are termed as aqua-privy. They can vary in the construction, given the available materials for the slab and shelter. Plate 1 shows a simple sketch of a pit latrine and Plate 2 shows an example of a typical traditional pit latrine in a rural area in Tanzania.

Plate 1: Simple sketch of a pit latrine

Plate 2: Example of traditional pit latrine in a rural area in Tanzania

2.0 Materials and Methods

A major source of data for this paper is the household baseline survey that place between December 2010 and June 2011 and the end line survey – took place between April and June 2014. For the end line survey households which were interviewed in the baseline survey were revisited to measure changes over time. The baseline survey offers a snapshot of living conditions, social life and public

facilities in Tanzania and the end line survey provides an opportunity for assessments of changes over time. The household sampling, interviewing, data preparation and data cleaning were carried out by Ipsos/Synovate for the baseline survey and by Economic Development Initiative (EDI) for the end line survey.

2.1 Community sampling

The sample was meant to represent communities, which were randomly selected (see paragraph below). The sample was designed to be informative in several subdivisions. Urban and rural communities were to be more or less equally represented; the sample was to cover all regions within the country, aggregated into the seven zones of Tanzania; the sample included a sufficient number of communities targeted by the Uwezo initiative. In all the zones some villages had already experienced, prior to the baseline, one Twaweza intervention, namely the learning assessment. Since the Uwezo villages were selected randomly the effect of the intervention can be inferred through comparison with a control group of non-test villages. For other interventions, the fact that the Uwezo test preceded the baseline survey is a serious disadvantage. This was an argument for limiting the number of Uwezo villages in the sample. These two considerations were reconciled by oversampling Uwezo villages but only to a limited extent. A third of the villages were sampled from the Uwezo test villages. By sampling Uwezo villages only from the five zones with the largest population (Central, Eastern, Lake, Northern and Southern Highlands zones) the share of Uwezo villages in those zones is 50% which maximizes the statistical power of comparison tests between Uwezo and non-Uwezo villages.

The sample composition by zone, Uwezo status, and rural/urban status is shown in Table 1 below. This composition implies a share of 49% of urban locations (mtaa) and 36% percent of Uwezo villages, close to the objectives of 50% and 33% respectively. In the original sample of Uwezo villages, the share of urban locations in each district is approximately equal to the urban population share, resulting in an overall 26% share of urban locations. Inflating the 26% to the target of 50% would, however, have led to excessively high urban shares in some zones (up to 82%). The number of urban locations in those zones (Eastern and Southern Highlands zones) was, therefore, reduced and the number of urban locations in the less urbanized zones (Southern and Western zones) was increased as compensation.

Table 1: Twaweza baseline survey, planned sample composition

Zone	Uwezo villages	Uwezo locations (mtaa)	Non-Uwezo villages	Non-Uwezo locations (mtaa)	Total
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	
Central	9	9	9	9	36
Eastern	7	11	7	11	36
Lake	8	10	8	10	36
Northern	9	9	9	9	36
SHL	7	11	7	11	36
Southern			24	11	35
Western			24	11	35
Total	40	50	88	72	250

To select locations into the survey a list of all locations within each cell of the Table above was first made from which the required number of locations was then randomly selected. The probability for a location to be selected was proportional to its population size in order to avoid over-representation of very small villages. The list of selected villages was handed over to Ipsos/Synovate, a firm specialized in conducting surveys. Ipsos/Synovate was responsible for the household listing and selection.

2.2 Household sampling

The plan was to sample 10 households from locations that were not reached by the Uwezo program and up to 19 households from locations that were covered by Uwezo: 10 households that were not involved in Uwezo, and up to 9 Uwezo households, depending on the number of Uwezo households that could be found.

The ultimate sample composition achieved is given in Table 2. A cell showing 9/170 means that that particular cell includes 9 sampled locations and a total of 170 households from those 9 locations. The Table shows that a total of 260 locations and 3296 households have been sampled.

Table 2: Twaweza baseline survey: final sample composition of household survey

Zone	Uwezo villages	Uwezo locations (mtaa)	Non-Uwezo villages	Non-Uwezo locations (mtaa)	Total
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	
Central	9/170	9/160	9/91	9/89	36/510
Eastern	9/142	11/185	6/65	12/156	38/548
Lake	9/162	13/198	8/75	11/105	41/540

Northern	9/161	10/183	11/108	8/76	38/528
SHL	7/131	12/200	7/68	11/111	37/510
Southern			24/215	11/107	35/322
Western			23/220	12/118	35/338
Total	43/766	55/926	88/842	74/762	260/3296

A map of all the sampled locations is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Map of Tanzania showing sampled location

3.0 Findings

3.1 Traditional pit latrine situation

According to the baseline, the situation of the traditional pit latrines is as summarized in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Baseline results

According to these results, there were more traditional pit latrines in the rural areas compared to the urban. Generally, however, the coverage is close to three-quarters.

In the end line, the situation of the traditional pit latrines is as summarized in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: End line results

According to these results, still, there were more traditional pit latrines in the rural areas compared to the urban. Generally, however, the coverage is beyond three-quarters.

3.2 Outcomes

The comparison of the situation between the baseline and end line in rural areas is summarized in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: Baseline and end line situation of traditional pit latrines in Rural Tanzania.

The findings show that there is a drop of traditional pit latrines by 0.6%. However, looking at the P-value, which is 0.650, the difference is not significant.

The comparison of the situation between the baseline and end line in urban areas is summarized in Figure 5 below:

Figure 5: Baseline and end line situation of traditional pit latrines in urban areas

The findings show that there is an increase in the traditional pit latrines by 9.7%. And looking at the P-value, which is 0.000, the difference is significant, implying that there is a perceptible increase in the use of traditional pit latrines in urban areas.

The comparison of the situation between the baseline and end line in both urban and rural areas is summarized in Figure 6 below:

Figure 6: Situation of tradition pit latrines for rural and urban combined

The findings show that there is an increase in the traditional pit latrines by 4.8%. And looking at the P-value, which is 0.000, the difference is significant, implying that there is generally a perceptible increase in the use of traditional pit latrines.

4.0 Discussion of the findings

The finding that there is no significant difference between the baseline and end line situation in rural areas implies that the use of traditional pit latrines has actually not changed that much. This finding means that significantly people have not gone back to open defecation, which is a good thing, but they have actually even not improved in the toilet facilities, for instance getting to ventilated improved pit latrines. Given that this is a rural area, this is caused by lack of the felt need. In this line, Menon (2015) observes that toilet use is not a 'felt need' in many parts of the country as the majority (more than 70%) live in rural areas where availability of bushes, forest and farm lands provide an option for practicing open defecation.

The finding that there is a significant increase in the traditional pit latrines by 9.7% in urban and a general trend whereby there is an increase in the traditional pit latrines by 4.8% implies a reduction of

open defecation and a step towards having a toilet facility. This is likely because of the efforts of improving hygiene. Initiatives to access "improved" sanitation have been in place in many part of the country including recognition by the National Sanitation policy of 2009 and the Community Led Total Sanitation (CLTS) approach, which is hailed for promotion of behavioral change that motivates use of latrines with little support both financially and technically from outside the intended society (Kar & Chambers, 2008; Kasper, 2013; Rognerud, & Fonseca, 2016; Chambers & Myers, 2016). Constructing and using a toilet has been assigned to the head of household by the National Sanitation and Hygiene Policy of 2009 (URT, 2009); toilet use has become a point of accountability.

5.0 Conclusion and recommendations

The study has shown the increase in the use of traditional pit latrines in general and in the urban areas. This is a sign of reduction of open defecation. This is a positive change in the improved toilet facility use. As the policy already demands accountability of the construction and use of toilet facilities, there is a need for more efforts in the rural areas to make a follow up to the head of household. This effort should be accompanied by "micro" land use planning at the household level and promotion of ventilated pit latrine toilet facilities. Proper procedures to identify and allocate space for a toilet facility on the household plot are necessary.

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